

ELEMENTS OF CREDIT POLICY AND STIMULATION OF CREDIT INVESTMENTS IN THE REAL ECONOMY

Ibrahimova S.

Associate Professor of Odlar Yurdu University, Baku, Azerbaijan

Orujov M.

Honorary Professor of SMBS (Swiss Montreux Business School),

Odlar Yurdu University, Baku, Azerbaijan

Orujov A.

Assistant teacher, Odlar Yurdu University, Baku, Azerbaijan

ABSTRACT

The purpose of the study is the study of credit policy in the Republic of Azerbaijan for the possibility of increasing the effectiveness of credit investments in the real economy and the direction of its improvement. Methodology of research - such general theoretical methods as analysis and synthesis, deduction and induction, generalization of reference and scientific literature, theoretical modeling, grouping methods and comparisons were used during the research. Practical significance of research - analysis of export - import operations and the state of trade turnover in the country. The results of the research - the analysis carried out in the article showed that the market of goods and services for priority development requires the improvement of non-cash money circulation in the country. The originality and scientific novelty of the research consists in the development of recommendations for improving export positions in the Republic of Azerbaijan.

Keywords: trade, export, import, trade balance, monetary turnover, investment.

Introduction

Over one and a half thousand units of agricultural machinery and equipment were imported through "Agroleasing" and leased to farmers on preferential terms. According to the decision taken by the relevant state commission, in 2022, over one and a half thousand agricultural producers were allocated subsidies in the amount of 45 million manat.

During 2023, up to 165,000 meters of collector and drainage networks, more than 209,000 meters of irrigation canals were built and reconstructed on agricultural lands. Along with this, the construction of the Shamkir reservoir, the Upper Mil Canal, and the Takhtakorpyun reservoir was completed. Today, most of them are already successfully functioning. The Samur-Absheron Canal was reconstructed.

Cotton growing, sericulture, tobacco growing, and hazelnut growing also have great potential for export. The development of this sector will also have a positive impact on the urbanization process. It will provide employment to the population in the regions, rural areas, and improve the standard of living of people.

Over the past 5-6 years, the government has been implementing a number of measures aimed at developing tourism. The government is quite clearly aware that this requires the adoption of a set of measures to improve the activities of companies operating in this sector, which, in turn, requires a high level of services provided and professionalism of the workforce.

In order to develop tourism, it is necessary to stimulate tourism activities in the regions in this area, strengthen information and propaganda work corresponding to the priority development of tourist routes, which will contribute to successful development in the post-pandemic period. It is also necessary to take into account that in the post-pandemic period in 2020, the protection of socially sensitive groups of the population was strengthened (increase in pensions and social benefits, targeted social assistance, monthly food benefits for internally displaced persons, etc.), and the salaries

of workers in healthcare, culture, sports, science and the agricultural sector increased by 10%. All this required diversification of the national economy, which was also shown in 2017, when significant reforms were carried out, the goals of which were the modernization and diversification of the national economy through the prevailing development of the non-oil sector, improvement of the market mechanism, state support for entrepreneurship and private business.

The strategic roadmap has ensured and will ensure the growth of competitiveness of domestic production. Responding to global challenges and as a result of attracting investments, developing a free business environment, entering markets and human capital, Azerbaijan has shown itself on the world pedestal as a country that has entered the group of high-income countries. For this purpose, four strategic goals were selected within the framework of the national economic prospects. As a result of the implementation of these goals and strategic roadmaps for 11 sectors, sustainable development has become a priority by ensuring a balance between the real and financial sectors. In this regard, it should be noted that the goal of ensuring fiscal sustainability has been achieved in Azerbaijan, and the monetary policy is based on the floating exchange rate regime. Putting fiscal and monetary policies in order ensured macroeconomic stability. The second goal in the national economic prospects was to increase the rationality of the activities of legal entities, controlling stakes and ensuring the dynamism of the economy through privatization. The third goal is related to the development of human capital. Finally, the fourth goal implied an even greater improvement of the business environment in the future.

The most clearly visible data can be found in the data of the State Committee of Azerbaijan for 2023 on exports and imports, which is an economic model suitable for Azerbaijan, i.e. an export-oriented model (Table 1).

Table 1.

Major export countries		
Name of countries	Thousand US Dollars	Compared to total export volume, in %
Total	33,898,554.9	100.0
Including:		
Italy	1,520,8067.6	44.9
Turkey	5,359,328.1	15.8
Russia	1,196,411.3	3.5
Greece	1,363,448.3	4.0
Croatia	590,440.5	1.7
Georgia	759,444.5	2.2
China	78,739.1	0.2
India	1,234,731.0	3.6
Israel	1,401,607.3	4.1
Spain	785,367.8	2.3
Ukraine	118,645.8	0.4
Portugal	299,628.3	0.9
Germany	907,923.0	2.7
Czech Republic	6,84,215.5	2.0
Great Britain	447,910.5	1.3
Bulgaria	481,926.3	1.4
France	1,33,219.5	0.4
Romania	604,469.4	1.8
Vietnam	345,757.1	1.0
Other countries	1,897,274.0	5.6

Source: Statistical Indicators of the Republic of Azerbaijan-2023

Table 2.

Main import countries		
Name of countries	Thousand US Dollars	Compared to total export volume, in %
Total	17285344.7	100.0
Including		
Russia	3162328.9	18.3
Turkey	2291271.4	13.3
China	3022810.5	17.5
USA	888168.9	5.1
Germany	916421.2	5.3
France	403052.0	2.3
Ukraine	235128.8	1.4
Italy	477904.0	2.8
Great Britain	342873.7	2.0
Iran	473087.3	2.7
Japan	435287.7	2.5
Korea	428091.1	2.5
India	200771.5	1.2
Spain	103138.4	0.6
Kazakhstan	215638.8	1.2
Other countries	3689370.5	21.3

Source: Statistical indicators of the Republic of Azerbaijan-2023

Additionally, Azerbaijan offers great opportunities for foreign investors, having made significant in-

vestments in the development and enhancement of infrastructure, increasing transit capabilities, and improving the business environment.

Diagram 1. Structure of credit investments by credit institutions, in % (01.01.2024)

Increasing the investment attractiveness of Azerbaijan for foreign investors involves simplifying business visas. It is necessary to continue reforming the customs system and encouraging the practice of foreign companies to attract labor resources. In addition, the transition to electronic document flow is currently being actively implemented. Thus, entrepreneurs will need only two documents to carry out export-import operations. As a result of reforms aimed at liberalizing export-import operations, since January 1, 2009, the "single window" principle has been applied when checking goods and vehicles passing through the border, and with the application of the new Customs Code, administrative procedures related to a number of export-import operations have been simplified once again. It should also be taken into account that along with improving conditions for foreign entities, it is necessary to protect the domestic market as much as possible, that is, by increasing customs duties, reduce imports of products and increase sales of local products with low cost.

Thus, a set of measures, ranging from supporting the production of products oriented towards export to directly simplifying the procedures for their sale, will become the foundation for the implementation of plans to diversify the economy of the republic.

We believe it is necessary to study the issues related to the theory of supply and demand when studying the causes of economic crises. The main ones, in our opinion, are the problems of correctly determining the level of taxation. Tax rates are directly related to the level of production and its absolute volume. Unreasonably high tax rates practically do not stimulate production growth due to the lack of the ability to pay them. In some cases, production is suspended, in others, the profile of work is changed to such an activity where tax rates are relatively low, and in the third, an opportunity is found to switch to illegal working conditions.

Tax rates can be increased until the achieved level becomes an obstacle to production and tax revenues to the treasury. The optimal level of tax rates should be determined by the government of each country depending on the current economic situation. As a rule, an unjustified increase in tax rates gives the opposite effect. Studying this dependence, the American economist Arthur B. Laffer was the first to construct a graphical

model, where he theoretically substantiated the optimal point of tax rates. This curve has since gained sufficient popularity among economists involved in both taxation and economic development issues.

However, J. Keynes also pointed out that in order to get the economy out of such a situation, mandatory government intervention is necessary, mainly with the help of fiscal and monetary levers.

In his opinion, the government should actively interfere in the processes with the help of specially developed programs that provide not only for the aggregate volume of money supply and money demand, but also include such parameters as the minimum wage, price, and interest rate. International financial institutions have been guided by these provisions for a long period of time to stabilize the economies of developing countries. However, as already noted, in the early seventies, when other processes were taking place in the world economy that did not fall under Keynesian definitions, economists began to study in more detail the causes of sharp fluctuations in the economy. Thus, after many decades of dominance of Keynes's theories, alternative ideas have emerged that make it possible to more accurately determine the causes of fluctuations in the world economy. Unlike Keynes, the supporters of the new idea believed that the market itself is self-regulating, that is, they returned to the definitions of Adam Smith. In their opinion, strong government intervention in the economy ultimately does not provide an opportunity for its normal development.

There are two main ways to solve such issues. The first is the Keynesian method, and the second is the monetaristic approach.

The option proposed by Keynesians to prevent high inflation or hyperinflation mainly involves cutting government spending and revising tax policy. At the same time, it is also considered acceptable to control wages, prices, and the interest rate on bank loans. In addition, Keynesians note the special role of the volume of money supply. Unlike Keynesians, monetarists are more specific. To resolve this problem, they propose only to limit the volume of money supply. If we approach the analysis of the high inflation caused by the high level in more detail, we can see that both options propose to reduce the volume of money supply. The only difference is that in some sentences this is

done in a more its expanded form, and in others - more specifically.

Diagram 2. Amount of cash and non-cash money turnover for 2023.

As we can see from diagram 2, the amount of cash in circulation exceeds bank reserves. That is, the release of cash into circulation in national currency should be reduced to a minimum, so the share of the money supply in relation to GDP will sharply decrease and the economy will be demonetized, which will necessarily affect the level of production and effective demand.

Thus, by maximally reducing or eliminating individual budget expenditures, as well as practically suspending bank lending and tightening control over the

release of cash into circulation, the intended goals will be achieved. All these measures will ultimately make it possible to sharply reduce the amount of cash in circulation, which will reduce the need for hard currency at all levels - thereby creating the possibility of regulating the level of inflation as a whole with a significant, as a rule, decline in production.

Table 3.

Major countries of trade turnover		
Name of countries	Thousand US Dollars	Relative to trade turnover in %
Total	51183899.6	100.0
Including		
Italy	15685971.6	3.1
Turkey	7650599.5	1.5
Russia	4358740.2	8.5
Greece	1395789.9	2.7
Croatia	595225.6	1.2
Georgia	885826.1	1.7
China	3101549.6	6.1
India	333991.0	0.6
Israel	1443519.7	2.8
Iran	487394.7	0.9
Spain	888506.2	1.7
France	536271.5	1.0
Ukraine	353774.6	0.7
Portugal	313361.8	0.6
Germany	1824344.2	3.6
Czech Republic	767269.6	1.5
Great Britain	790784.2	1.5
Bulgaria	510930.7	1.0
Romania	670128.3	1.3
Vietnam	482093.3	0.9
USA	904180.3	1.8
Belarus	356589.4	0.7
Turkmenistan	773908.1	1.5
Other countries	6073149.5	11.9

Source: Statistical indicators of the Republic of Azerbaijan

It should be noted that an equally important object of macroeconomic research is the country's foreign economic activity. For example, the country's trade balance, which in turn indicates the state of the economy of each country. As we can see from the table, a positive balance indicates an excess of exports over imports, which creates a positive dynamic for the country's development. The reform of the financial sector began in 1992, when a two-tier banking system was introduced.

The procedure for allocating loans was determined in accordance with the annual credit plan, which was approved by parliament. The Central Bank did not control foreign exchange reserves, which were mainly allocated through the foreign exchange budget for state needs, including national security and defense. Differentiated requirements for the mandatory sale of foreign currency at rates below the market rate led to the formation of multiple exchange rates. Only in January 1994, the manat, the national currency of Azerbaijan, became the only legal tender in the country, which provided a certain autonomy to the monetary and credit

regulation authorities. In the current economic situation, characterized by systemic changes and external shocks, the pursued financial policy did not meet the objectives of stabilizing the economy. Due to the decrease in the level of state revenues, the budget situation deteriorated sharply. This occurred, first of all, as a result of the reduction in production volume and the increase in the role of the informal sector in the economy.

However, the highest productivity growth in 2023 was observed in the information and communications sector - by 6.6%, to 1.724 billion manats. The share of the non-oil sector in the country's GDP was 62.6%. Non-oil exports grew by a record 10.5%, while total exports decreased by 33.7% compared to 2022. Official inflation in the country was observed at the level of 5.4%. During the year, the manat remained stable against the dollar, but devalued by twelve percent against the euro. As a result, according to the results of the year, GDP per capita amounted to 12114.5 manats. According to forecasts, GDP growth in 2024 will be 4.7%. In 2023 - 1.1%, in 2022 - 4.6%, in 2021 - 5.6%.

Table 4.

Main indicators of the state budget of the Republic of Azerbaijan

Years	Budget revenues, million manat	Share of GDP, in %	Budget expenditures, million manat	Share of GDP, in %	Budget deficit(-) Surplus(+) million manat	Share of GDP, in %
2012	17281,6	32,0	17105,6	31,7	176,0	0,3
2015	17153,2	31,6	17786,8	32,7	-633,6	-1,2
2017	16446,9	23,5	17588,4	25,1	-1141,5	-1,6
2018	22411,2	28,1	22718,9	28,5	-307,7	-0,4
2019	24199,6	29,6	24404,8	59,9	-205,2	-0,3
2020	24681,7	34,1	26416,3	36,5	-1734,6	-2,4
2021	26396,3	28,3	27422,4	29,4	-1026,1	-1,1
2022	30679,6	22,9	32064,6	23,9	-1385,0	-1,0
2023	35236,4	28,6	36458,0	29,6	-1221,6	-1,0

Source: Statistical indicators of the Republic of Azerbaijan-2023

As shown in Table 4, it is evident that expenditures grow in line with budget revenues, but despite the state budget deficit, it still does not exceed 3% of GDP. The budget system of Azerbaijan is the most important link in the republic's financial system. It includes the republican budget and local budgets. Local budgets are divided into city, village and town budgets. City budgets, in turn, consist of city budgets, city district budgets, village and town subordination budgets. The tasks performed with the help of the budget provide grounds for defining the essence of the budget. Without going into detail about the polemics about the essence, functions and principles of budget construction, we nevertheless believe it is necessary to define the initial theoretical positions on these concepts, which have been controversial to date. For the most effective management of the budget process, it is of fundamental importance how the term "budget" itself is defined. In most cases, this concept is limited to estimates related to annual allocations of funds by the relevant legislative body. Such a concept, however, can cover only a small share of all budget and tax operations. As has already been said above, the volume of long-term loans to the econ-

omy, which are the basis for its development, contributed to the smooth operation of financial and economic structures. For example, deliberate stimulation of issuing short-term trade loans led to the fact that most private enterprises began to closely engage in the export of various consumer (mainly food) goods. Naturally, here certain interests of enterprises engaged in the export of goods to the country were stimulated by maximizing profits compared to production.

CONCLUSION

The very emergence of a deficit is evidence of a shortage of budget revenues to cover existing government expenditures. It should be noted that the main thing is that the definition of all sources of income remains unbalanced, and what is no less important, what part of the expenses can be considered quite justified. The availability of alternative sources for covering the resulting deficit is also of no small importance. After all, in principle, the budget deficit can be covered by not one, but several sources, including such an inflationary source as a loan from the Central Bank. Determining the most acceptable option for covering the budget deficit can only take place if the government has

a financial and budgetary policy that is justified for the given stage of economic development.

References

1. Laws of the Republic of Azerbaijan on the state budget of Azerbaijan for 2023(in Azerbaijan)
2. Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan "On the National Bank of the Republic of Azerbaijan". – Baku 10.06.1996. - No. 118-1G // Businessman's Bulletin. - 1996. - No. 32. (in Azerbaijan)
3. M.M. Orucov "The modern development model of the national economy" The scientific and pedagogical news of Odlar Yurdu № 54. (in Azerbaijan)
4. Godzhaeva E.M. Finances of foreign countries and international credit relations. - Baku: "NURLAR", 2021, - 475 p. (in Azerbaijan)
5. Kuliye R.A. Transitional economy of Azerbaijan: some aspects of development. - Baku, 2007. – 74 p. (in Azerbaijan)
6. "Strategic roadmap for the national economy" from 2016.7. S.Ibrahimova, M. Orujov Monetary stabilization policy during the financial crisis XIV (in Azerbaijan) International Scientific Conference. Tokyo. Japan 2024
8. Efendiyev O.F., Aliyev E.A. Foreign economic activity of modern Azerbaijan. Study guide. Baku, Publishing and printing enterprise "Zardabi LTD" LLC, 2007, p. 328. (in Azerbaijan)
9. M.M. Orucov Modern development model of the national economy. Scientific and Pedagogical News of OYU, 2020, (in Azerbaijan)
10. Rakhmanov F., Suleymanov E., Godzhaeva E. Economy of Azerbaijan. "University Publishing House named after Saints Cyril and Methodius". Veliko Tarnovo – 2021, p. 420. (in Azerbaijan)